

CAUSES OF INSTABILITY OF EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCES IN MODERN ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the author talks about the development of the emotional sphere, the functions and components of emotions, reveals the causes of emotional instability in adolescents. He also presented the results of his study of the speed of manifestation of emotional experiences in adolescents.

As one of the leading factors, the emotional sphere characterizes the social processes as well as the individual and determines the subjective quality of the individual's life. The modern social environment, with huge information loads, instability, stressful pace of life, many ways of self-determination and competition, puts new demands on the possibilities of the emotional sphere of the individual. In this way, it is required that a person perfects the ability to manage his emotional state and maintain emotional stability in order to achieve success and solve important life tasks.

Emotions express our reaction to the information we learn and our actions. Knowledge of emotions is necessary for each of us to better understand ourselves and others. It is impossible to live without emotions.

Emotional sphere plays an important role in personality development. However, its violation leads to imbalance in personality development, especially in adolescence. Adolescence is recognized as a period of transition, crisis and turning point in a person's life. Changes in the physiology of the body, the adolescent's relationship with adults and peers, the development of cognitive processes, the level of intelligence and ability in them cause high emotionality, aggressiveness, sudden changes in mood, impressionability, as a result of which, easy excitement, tendency to stress, the emergence of anxiety and other changes. Adolescence is considered an "emotionally rich" period, and therefore the study of the emotional development of adolescents occupies a leading place in psychology.

S. L. Rubinstein emphasizes that emotions reflect a person's overall attitude to the world and behavior (or what happens to him) in accordance with his needs. "A person's feeling is his attitude to the world, what he feels and what he does in the form of direct experiences" [4].

Emotions (from the Latin *emovere* - arousal, excitement) are a condition related to the assessment of the importance of factors affecting him and, first of all, expressed in the form of experiences of direct satisfaction or non-satisfaction of his most important needs. Emotions

are one of the main regulators of activity. Usually, emotions are defined as a specific type of mental processes that represent the experiences of a person's attitude to the environment and to himself. The characteristic of emotions is that they directly assess the importance of objects and feelings that affect a person depending on the needs of the subject [2].

V. Gaylin [1] distinguishes three main functions of emotions:

- 1) ensuring survival of individuals and groups;
- 2) showing insufficiently effective human performance;
- 3) to show group life content as well as individual.

Emotions influence the expression of human experiences. In this case, the mood is determined not by the immediate consequences of one or another event, but by the emotional reaction to its importance for a person for his general life plans. Most people's moods fluctuate between moderately disappointed and moderately elated. People vary greatly in the speed with which they change from happy to sad or vice versa.

Emotions also affect the sphere of perception: memory, thinking, imagination. Negative emotions give rise to feelings of sadness, mourning, despair, envy, malice, besides, if repeated often, they can provoke psychogenic skin diseases: eczema, neurodermatitis, secretory and trophic changes of the skin - hair loss or graying. Serious emotional stress can manifest itself in various painful sensations, such as frequent sweating, nausea, loss or increase in appetite, and increased thirst. Emotions and thinking are interconnected, and therefore there is a reciprocal relationship between the character of the thoughts that come to the brain and the mood. So, the general condition of a person is effectively affected by pleasant thoughts that are able to solve any complex task.

Emotions are a complex mental process consisting of three main components:

1. Physiological - reflects the physiological changes that occur when emotions are formed (changes in heart rate, increased breathing, metabolic processes, hormonal changes, etc.).
2. Psychological - personal experiences (joy, sadness, fear, etc.).
3. Behavioral - expression (mimicry, gestures) and various actions (fleeing, fighting, etc.).

In the existential-humanistic paradigm, K. Rogers [3] associates unpleasant or arousing emotions with "seeking behavior", defines the concept of "good life" under this concept as openness to one's subjective experience - subjective experiences, including heartache, suffering, fear and loyalty return, etc. includes one of the aspects of the action process from the pole of the protective reaction to the opening ability. It's about being aware of your life in the present moment. The flow of real reality, surrender to its content, ensures the fullness of experiences, the enrichment of personal existence. Expressing one's feelings in the "here and now" situation allows a person to subjectively experience emotional well-being.

As part of our research on "Characteristics of psychological development of children growing up in the families of labor migrants", we conducted a survey with 130 high school students of the general secondary school in the city of Fergana to find out how often teenagers feel specific emotions.

If we take into account that the inadequate emotional experience received in childhood (in turbulent families, in the case of a broken relationship between parents and children or between parents) is reflected in the general emotional development of the child, emotional

disturbances and emotional instability are also observed in adolescents whose father or mother has left for labor migration. occurs in the following cases:

- family turmoil,
- neurosis of father or mother,
- quarrels in the family,
- family members' behavior;
- the collapse of the family.

Although the results of the "Differential Emotions Scale" method show no significant difference in the indicators of teenagers who are children of families affected by labor migration and families not affected by labor migration, it can be said that the expression of emotions is high in adolescents who are near their parents and relatives. This is because they:

- did not accept the information with indifference or concern when working with each methodology was explained;
- they did not show difficulty while working with the methodology;
- did not hesitate to express their true feelings.

Marital status of respondents	Index of positive emotions (interest, joy, surprise)	Index of severe negative emotions (sadness, anger, suspicion, disgust)	Index of anxious-depressed emotions (fear, shame, guilt)
Families of labor migrants	63-66	63-70	63-65
Families not affected by labor migration	67-70	67-72	67-69

In conclusion, it can be said that adolescents from families where one of their relatives has left for labor migration often try to hide or present their true experiences in a different way. This causes emotional instability in them.

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